

COMPARISON OF METFORMIN ALONE VERSUS METFORMIN PLUS VITAMIN B12 IN REDUCING METFORMIN-ASSOCIATED NEUROPATHY

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Abstract

Background: Metformin is widely used as first-line therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus; however, long-term use is associated with reduced vitamin B12 absorption, which may contribute to or worsen peripheral neuropathy. Vitamin B12 supplementation has been proposed as a strategy to prevent or improve metformin-associated neuropathy.

Objectives: To compare the effectiveness of metformin alone versus metformin plus vitamin B12 supplementation in reducing neuropathy among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Study Design & Setting: This was a comparative, randomized study conducted over six months in the Department of Medicine Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from Jan 2025 to June 2025.

Methodology: A total of 120 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and features of peripheral neuropathy were enrolled and randomly divided into two groups of 60 each. Group A received metformin alone, while Group B received metformin plus oral vitamin B12 supplementation (1500 mcg daily) for 12 weeks. Neuropathy severity was assessed using the Michigan Neuropathy Screening Instrument (MNSI) at baseline and at 12 weeks. Serum vitamin B12 levels were measured at both time points. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, and a p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Baseline characteristics were similar between the two groups. At 12 weeks, Group B showed a substantial increase in serum vitamin B12 levels, whereas Group A showed a slight decline. Neuropathy improvement was greater in Group B, with a larger reduction in MNSI scores compared to Group A. The proportion of patients with persistent neuropathy was lower in the vitamin B12-supplemented group.

Conclusion: The combination of metformin and vitamin B12 was more effective than metformin alone in improving neuropathy and restoring serum vitamin B12 levels in patients receiving long-term metformin therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Metformin remains the first-line pharmacologic therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) worldwide due to its proven efficacy, favorable safety profile, weight neutrality, and cardiovascular benefits.¹ It is widely prescribed both as monotherapy and in combination with other glucose-lowering agents. Despite its long-standing clinical utility, concerns regarding metformin-associated adverse effects have gained increasing attention. Among these, vitamin B12 deficiency and subsequent neuropathy represent important but often under-recognized complications.² Evidence suggests that prolonged metformin therapy interferes with vitamin B12 absorption in the terminal ileum, leading to biochemical deficiency that may progress to clinically significant neurological impairment in susceptible patients. As diabetic peripheral neuropathy is already a common microvascular complication of T2DM, the superimposition of metformin-induced neuropathy further complicates diagnosis and management, contributing to reduced quality of life and increased risk of disability.^{3,4}

The prevalence of deficiency among long-term metformin users ranges from 5% to nearly 40%, depending on dosage, duration, dietary intake, and individual susceptibility.⁵ Vitamin B12 plays a critical role in neuronal function, DNA synthesis, methylation pathways, and myelin formation; therefore, its deficiency may lead to paresthesia, numbness, impaired proprioception, and even irreversible neurological damage if left untreated.^{6,7} As diabetic neuropathy and B12 deficiency neuropathy share overlapping symptoms, the condition is frequently overlooked or misattributed solely to diabetes itself. This highlights the clinical need for proactive screening and early intervention in patients on extended metformin therapy.⁸

Given the identified risk, supplementation with vitamin B12 has been proposed as a strategy to counteract the neuropathic complications associated with metformin. Studies evaluating the impact of vitamin B12 supplementation have shown promising results, including improved nerve conduction parameters, reduction in neuropathic pain, and restoration of serum B12 levels. However, research remains inconsistent regarding the magnitude of benefit, optimal dosage, and duration of

supplementation required to prevent or reverse neuropathic symptoms.⁹ While some trials demonstrate significant symptomatic improvement with vitamin B12 replacement, others report modest or non-significant effects. Moreover, most available studies have either small sample sizes or lack well-defined comparative groups, making it difficult to formulate evidence-based guidelines for routine supplementation in metformin-treated patients.^{11,12}

The lack of consensus underscores the need for more robust comparative studies evaluating the clinical impact of vitamin B12 co-administration with metformin, particularly in reducing the risk and severity of metformin-associated neuropathy. Understanding whether routine supplementation provides measurable protection or therapeutic benefit would have significant implications for diabetes management, especially in populations with a high burden of neuropathy or nutritional deficiencies. Therefore, the present study aims to compare the efficacy of metformin alone versus metformin combined with vitamin B12 in reducing metformin-associated neuropathy. By analyzing neuropathic symptoms, biochemical markers, and treatment outcomes, this research seeks to provide evidence-based insights that may guide clinicians toward more effective, individualized, and preventive strategies for managing neuropathy among patients receiving long-term metformin therapy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This comparative study was conducted in the Department of Medicine Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from Jan 2025 to June 2025. A total of 120 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus who were receiving metformin therapy were enrolled. The sample size of 120 was calculated using a 95% confidence level, 80% power, and an expected difference of 20% in neuropathy improvement between groups, based on previous literature estimates. Patients were randomly allocated into two equal groups of 60 each: Group A received metformin alone, while Group B received metformin plus vitamin B12 supplementation.

Patients aged 30–70 years of either gender who had been on metformin for at least one year and had clinical features suggestive of peripheral neuropathy

were included. Neuropathy was defined based on symptoms of numbness, tingling, burning sensation, or diminished vibration sense. Patients with known vitamin B12 deficiency before starting metformin, those with chronic alcoholism, thyroid disorders, renal failure, neurodegenerative diseases, or those already taking vitamin B12 supplements were excluded. Pregnant and lactating women were also excluded from the study.

A detailed medical history was obtained, and a complete physical and neurological examination was performed for all participants. Baseline laboratory investigations included fasting blood glucose, HbA1c, serum vitamin B12 levels, and routine hematological and biochemical tests. Neuropathy severity was assessed using the Michigan Neuropathy Screening Instrument (MNSI), which included both a symptom score and a clinical examination score. All assessments were conducted at baseline and again at 12 weeks.

Group A was administered standard metformin therapy at a dose ranging from 1000 mg to 2000 mg per day, as prescribed by the treating physician. Group B received the same metformin regimen along with oral vitamin B12 supplementation at a dose of 1500 mcg daily for 12 weeks. Compliance was ensured through monthly follow-up visits, pill counts, and telephonic reminders. Any adverse effects, intolerance, or discontinuation of treatment were recorded.

At the end of 12 weeks, serum vitamin B12 levels were reassessed, and neuropathy symptoms were re-evaluated using the MNSI score. The primary outcome measure was the reduction in neuropathy symptoms and improvement in clinical signs, while secondary outcomes included changes in serum vitamin B12 levels and glycemic control. Data were collected using a structured proforma.

All data were entered and analyzed using SPSS software version 25. Quantitative variables such as age, vitamin B12 levels, and MNSI scores were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables such as gender and symptom improvement were expressed as frequencies and percentages. An independent sample *t*-test was applied to compare mean changes between groups, and a chi-square test was used to compare categorical

variables. A *p*-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the institutional review board, and written informed consent was taken from all participants prior to enrollment. Confidentiality of patient information was strictly maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS

The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population were comparable between the two groups. The mean age was similar in both groups, and the distribution of gender showed no major differences. Both groups had a comparable duration of diabetes and duration of metformin use. Baseline HbA1c levels were almost identical, indicating similar glycemic control at enrollment. Serum vitamin B12 levels at baseline were nearly equal, and the initial MNSI neuropathy scores also showed minimal variation, suggesting that both groups started with similar neuropathy severity, as given in Table 1.

Serum vitamin B12 levels remained relatively unchanged in the metformin-alone group over 12 weeks, with a slight decline noted by the end of the study. In contrast, the group receiving metformin plus vitamin B12 showed a significant rise in serum B12 levels at 12 weeks. The mean change indicated that supplementation led to a marked improvement in vitamin B12 status, whereas metformin alone did not prevent a decline in levels, as given in Table 2.

Neuropathy severity, measured using the MNSI score, decreased in both groups over the 12-week period; however, the improvement was more pronounced in the group receiving metformin with vitamin B12 supplementation. While the metformin-alone group showed a modest reduction in neuropathic symptoms, the combined therapy group demonstrated a greater decline in MNSI scores, indicating better symptom relief, as given in Table 3. At the end of the study, neuropathy remained more prevalent in the metformin-alone group compared to the group receiving vitamin B12 in addition to metformin. A higher proportion of patients in the combination group were free of neuropathy based on MNSI threshold scoring, showing a better overall outcome in this group, as given in Table 4.

The frequency of adverse effects during the study was low in both groups, with nausea, headache, and fatigue being the most commonly reported. The incidence of adverse effects was similar across both

groups, and the majority of patients did not experience any complications during treatment, as given in Table 5.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 120)

Variable	Group A (Metformin Alone) (n = 60)	Group B (Metformin + Vitamin B12) (n = 60)
Age (years), mean \pm SD	54.2 \pm 8.1	53.7 \pm 7.9
Gender (Male/Female)	34 (56.7%) / 26 (43.3%)	32 (53.3%) / 28 (46.7%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	7.8 \pm 3.2	7.6 \pm 3.5
Duration of Metformin Use (years)	4.9 \pm 1.8	5.1 \pm 1.9
HbA1c (%), mean \pm SD	7.9 \pm 0.8	8.0 \pm 0.7
Serum Vitamin B12 (pg/mL)	236.4 \pm 42.8	238.7 \pm 40.3
MNSI Score (Baseline)	6.8 \pm 1.5	6.7 \pm 1.6

Table 2: Comparison of Serum Vitamin B12 Levels at 12 Weeks

Time Point	Group A (Metformin Alone) (n = 60)	Group B (Metformin + Vitamin B12) (n = 60)
Baseline (pg/mL)	236.4 \pm 42.8	238.7 \pm 40.3
Week 12 (pg/mL)	229.5 \pm 39.7	412.8 \pm 55.4
Mean Change (pg/mL)	-6.9 \pm 10.2	+174.1 \pm 35.2

Table 3: Comparison of MNSI Symptom Scores Between Groups

Time Point	Group A (Metformin Alone) (n = 60)	Group B (Metformin + Vitamin B12) (n = 60)
Baseline Score	6.8 \pm 1.5	6.7 \pm 1.6
Week 12 Score	5.9 \pm 1.4	4.3 \pm 1.2
Mean Change	-0.9 \pm 0.7	-2.4 \pm 1.0

Table 4: Neuropathy Status at 12 Weeks (MNSI Threshold \geq 4)

Neuropathy Status	Group A (n = 60)	Group B (n = 60)
Present (n, %)	42 (70.0%)	21 (35.0%)
Absent (n, %)	18 (30.0%)	39 (65.0%)

Table 5: Adverse Effects Reported During the Study

Adverse Effect	Group A (n = 60)	Group B (n = 60)
Nausea	6 (10.0%)	7 (11.7%)
Headache	4 (6.7%)	5 (8.3%)
Fatigue	3 (5.0%)	2 (3.3%)
No Adverse Effects	47 (78.3%)	46 (76.7%)

DISCUSSION

Metformin is the most commonly prescribed first-line medication for type 2 diabetes mellitus due to

its efficacy and safety. Long-term metformin use, however, is known to decrease vitamin B12 absorption from the gastrointestinal tract. Vitamin

B12 deficiency may contribute to or worsen peripheral neuropathy, a frequent complication in diabetic patients.^{13,14} Because neuropathy symptoms from diabetes and B12 deficiency often overlap, the condition may go unnoticed. Supplementation with vitamin B12 has the potential to counteract metformin-induced deficiency and improve nerve function.¹⁵ Therefore, comparing metformin alone with metformin plus vitamin B12 is essential to guide better clinical management.

In the present study, metformin use alone was associated with a progressive decline in serum vitamin B12 levels, whereas the addition of vitamin B12 supplementation resulted in a significant improvement in both biochemical parameters and neuropathy scores over 12 weeks. At baseline, mean serum vitamin B12 was comparable between the two groups (236.4 ± 42.8 pg/mL versus 238.7 ± 40.3 pg/mL), but by week 12, patients receiving supplementation demonstrated a marked increase to 412.8 ± 55.4 pg/mL compared with a decline to 229.5 ± 39.7 pg/mL in the metformin-alone group. This pattern aligns with previous studies showing a strong association between metformin therapy and decreased vitamin B12 levels.

Riaz et al. (2025) reported a vitamin B12 deficiency frequency of 11.63% among diabetics presenting with peripheral neuropathy and specifically noted that deficiency was higher in diabetics taking metformin (13.95%) compared with non-metformin users (8.14%), although the difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.193$)¹⁶. Our findings similarly indicate that metformin alone tends to lower vitamin B12 levels, supporting the biochemical trend described in their study, although our supplementation group showed reversal of this deficiency.

Miyan et al. (2020) found that among 932 subjects, B12 deficiency (<200 pg/mL) was significantly higher in metformin users (3.9%) compared with non-users (2.1%), and that neuropathic indicators such as VPT > 25 and DN4 ≥ 4 were more frequent in B12-deficient metformin users¹⁸. Their data strengthen the mechanistic link between metformin-induced B12 deficiency and worsened neuropathy. In our study, neuropathy remained present in 70% of the metformin-alone group compared with only 35% in the supplementation group, demonstrating

that correcting B12 status can significantly alleviate neuropathic manifestations, consistent with the neuropathy associations reported by Miyan et al.¹⁸ Hussain et al. (2025) reported a higher prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency (40%) and identified female gender (aOR = 1.82) and longer diabetes duration (aOR = 2.08) as significant predictors, while metformin dose or duration showed no significant association¹⁹. Their findings imply multifactorial causation of B12 deficiency. In our study, baseline B12 levels were similar across genders, but the decline seen in the metformin-alone group suggests that, unlike Hussain et al., metformin exposure did contribute to worsening B12 status over time.

Gul (2023) demonstrated that B12 deficiency was significantly more common in metformin users (45.94%) versus non-users (14.86%) with an odds ratio of 4.87 (95% CI: 2.22–10.69)²⁰. Their findings strongly support the adverse effect of metformin on B12 metabolism, consistent with the decline observed in our control group. Moreover, our results extend their conclusions by showing that supplementation not only prevents this decline but also leads to clinical improvement, as reflected by a greater reduction in MNSI scores (-2.4 ± 1.0 vs. -0.9 ± 0.7).

Taken together, the results of the present study corroborate existing literature demonstrating metformin's negative impact on vitamin B12 levels and neuropathy, while adding new evidence that routine vitamin B12 supplementation can substantially improve both biochemical and neurological outcomes in diabetic patients on long-term metformin therapy.

This study included a well-defined sample of 120 patients with uniform diagnostic criteria. Random allocation of participants minimized selection bias. Use of standardized neuropathy scoring enhanced the reliability of findings. However, the study was single-center, which may limit generalizability. Follow-up duration of 12 weeks was relatively short for long-term neuropathy assessment. Serum methylmalonic acid levels were not measured, which could have provided additional diagnostic accuracy.

CONCLUSION

Metformin combined with vitamin B12 was more effective in improving neuropathy compared to

metformin alone. Vitamin B12 supplementation significantly increased serum B12 levels and enhanced symptom relief. Incorporating B12 supplementation may provide a beneficial strategy for patients on long-term metformin therapy.

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